

Mater Misericordiae
University Hospital
Sisters of Mercy

Eccles Street, Dublin D07 R2WY, Ireland

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Siúrachá na Trícaire

Sráid Eccles, Baile Átha Cliath D07 R2WY, Éire

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Questionnaire ANTICIPATE STUDY

JL-COVID-19 version 3 dated 1 JULY 2020

APPENDIX 1. QUESTIONNAIRE TO BE USED AT FOLLOW UP.

Month 3 , 6 -12

Sponsor	Dr John Lambert
Protocol Number:	JL-COVID 19 version 4 dated 1 JULY 2020
Protocol Title:	JL-COVID-19 version 4
Principal Investigators	Dr John Lambert, Dr Aoife Cotter & Prof Walter Cullen
Sub-Investigators	Ms T McHugh, Ms Gordana Avramovic, Stephen Connolly, Dr Tara Mc Ginty, Eileen O'Connor
Study Coordinator	Gordana Avramovic
Study Subject Code	

SF12

1. In general, would you say your health is:

- Excellent (1)
Very Good (2)
Good (3)
Fair (4)
Poor (5)

The following two questions are about activities you might do during a typical day. Does YOUR HEALTH NOW LIMIT YOU in these activities? If so, how much?

2. MODERATE ACTIVITIES, such as moving a table, pushing a vacuum cleaner, bowling, or playing golf:

- Yes, Limited A Lot (1)
Yes, Limited A Little (2)
No, Not Limited At All (3)

3. Climbing SEVERAL flights of stairs:

- Yes, Limited A Lot (1)
Yes, Limited A Little (2)
No, Not Limited At All (3)

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During the PAST 4 WEEKS have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular activities AS A RESULT OF YOUR PHYSICAL HEALTH?

4. ACCOMPLISHED LESS than you would like: _____

Yes (1)

No (2)

5. Were limited in the KIND of work or other activities:

Yes (1)

No (2)

During the PAST 4 WEEKS, were you limited in the kind of work you do or other regular activities AS A RESULT OF ANY EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS (such as feeling depressed or anxious)?

6. ACCOMPLISHED LESS than you would like:

Yes (1)

No (2)

7. Didn't do work or other activities as CAREFULLY as usual:

Yes (1)

No (2)

8. During the PAST 4 WEEKS, how much did PAIN interfere with your normal work (including both work outside the home and housework)?

Not At All (1)

A Little Bit (2)

Moderately (3)

Quite A Bit (4)

Extremely (5)

The next three questions are about how you feel and how things have been DURING THE PAST 4 WEEKS. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the PAST 4 WEEKS –

9. Have you felt calm and peaceful?

All of the Time (1)

Most of the Time (2)

A Good Bit of the Time (3)

Some of the Time (4)

A Little of the Time (5)

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P0004 – Feb 19

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None of the Time (6)

10. Did you have a lot of energy?

All of the Time (1)

Most of the Time (2)

A Good Bit of the Time (3)

Some of the Time (4)

A Little of the Time (5)

None of the Time (6)

11. Have you felt downhearted and blue?

All of the Time (1)

Most of the Time (2)

A Good Bit of the Time (3)

Some of the Time (4)

A Little of the Time (5)

None of the Time (6)

12. During the PAST 4 WEEKS, how much of the time has your PHYSICAL HEALTH OR EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS interfered with your social activities (like visiting with friends, relatives, etc.)?

All of the Time (1)

Most of the Time (2)

A Good Bit of the Time (3)

Some of the Time (4)

A Little of the Time (5)

None of the Time (6)

PHQ2

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

Give answers as 0 to 3, using this scale:

1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things

0=Not at all;

1=Several days;

2=More than half the days;

3=Nearly every day

2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless

0=Not at all;

1=Several days;

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2=More than half the days;

3=Nearly every day

In the past month, have you...

Had nightmares about the event(s) or thought about the event(s) when you did not want to?

YES

NO

Tried hard not to think about the event(s) or went out of your way to avoid situations that reminded you of the event(s)?

YES

NO

Been constantly on guard, watchful, or easily startled?

YES

NO

Felt numb or detached from people, activities, or your surroundings?

YES

NO

Felt guilty or unable to stop blaming yourself or others for the event(s) or any problems the event(s) may have caused?

YES

NO

Study Specific Questions Examining Process Of Care

1. Within seven days of discharge,

Did you attend a GP / out of hours service

YES

NO

Did you attend a hospital

YES

NO

Did you stay overnight in hospital

YES

NO

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2. Within 30 days of discharge,

Did you attend a GP / out of hours service?

YES

NO

Did you attend a hospital?

YES

NO

Did you stay overnight in hospital?

YES

NO

3. Since being discharged from hospital, did you experience any health-related problems? If yes, what?

Depression Scale of PRIME-MD

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following:

Little interest or pleasure in doing things

0 Not at all

1 Several days

2 More than half the days

3 Nearly every day

Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless

0 Not at all

1 Several days

2 More than half the days

3 Nearly every day

Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much

0 Not at all

1 Several days

2 More than half the days

3 Nearly every day

Feeling tired or having little energy

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- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

Poor appetite or overeating

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

Feeling bad about yourself—or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed (Or the opposite—being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual)

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

Anxiety scale of PRIME-MD (GAD-7)

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems?

1. Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge

- 0 Not at all

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- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

2. Not being able to stop or control worrying

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

3. Worrying too much about different things

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

4. Trouble relaxing

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

5. Being so restless that it is hard to sit still

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

6. Becoming easily annoyed or irritable

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

7. Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen

- 0 Not at all
- 1 Several days
- 2 More than half the days
- 3 Nearly every day

IESR

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Below is a list of difficulties people sometimes have after stressful life events. Please read each item, and then indicate how distressing each difficulty has been for you DURING THE PAST SEVEN DAYS with respect to COVID 19 that occurred on _____ (date). How much have you been distressed or bothered by these difficulties? PLEASE TICK AS APPROPRIATE

		Not at all	A little bit	Moderately	Quite a bit	Extremely
1	Any reminder brought back feelings about it					
2	I had trouble staying asleep					
3	Other things kept making me think about it.					
4	I felt irritable and angry					
5	I avoided letting myself get upset when					
6	I thought about it or was reminded of it					
7	I thought about it when I didn't mean					
8	I felt as if it hadn't happened or wasn't real.					
9	I stayed away from reminders of it.					
10	Pictures about it popped into my mind.					
11	I was jumpy and easily startled.					
12	I tried not to think about it.					
13	I was aware that I still had a lot of feelings about it, but I didn't deal with them					
14	My feelings about it were kind of numb					
15	I found myself acting or feeling like I was back at that time.					
16	I had trouble falling asleep					
17	I had waves of strong feelings about it					
18	I tried to remove it from my memory.					
19	I had trouble concentrating.					
20	Reminders of it caused me to have physical reactions, such as sweating, trouble breathing, nausea, or a pounding heart.					

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		Not at all	A little bit	Moderately	Quite a bit	Extremely
21	I had dreams about it.					
22	I felt watchful and on-guard.					
23	I tried not to talk about it.					

AUDIT-C

How often do you have a drink containing alcohol?

- Never
- Monthly or less
- 2 to 4 times per month
- 2 to 3 times per week
- 4 or more times per week

How many units of alcohol do you drink on a typical day when you are drinking?

- 0 to 2
- 3 to 4
- 5 to 6
- 7 to 9
- 10 or more

How often have you had 6 or more units if female, or 8 or more if male, on a single occasion in the last year?

- Never
- Less than monthly
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily or almost daily

Free text questions on how outbreak impacted on mental health, wellbeing and personal circumstances

How did the pandemic impact on people living in your local neighbourhood?

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Their general health and wellbeing?

Their mental health and wellbeing?

Their personal circumstances?

Their daily activities?

BORG QUESTIONNAIRE

	Shortness of breath	At rest	During activity
0	Nothing at all	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
0.5	Very very slight	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Very slight	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Slight	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Somewhat severe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Severe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Very severe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	Very very severe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10	Maximal	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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